

STUDIES IN DEHYDRATION OF CASTOR OIL

BY V. A. SARAF AND K. K. DOLE

(A) Anthraquinone-1-sulphonic acid, (D) anthraquinone-2-sulphonic acid, (C) *p*-toluene-thiosulphonic acid, (E) metanilic acid, (B) methyl benzenesulphonate, (F) ethyl benzenesulphonate and (G) ethyl toluene-*p*-sulphonate have been studied with respect to their catalytic action in the dehydration of castor oil. (A) and (B) have been found as active dehydrating catalysts. The position of -SO₂H group has very little influence on their catalytic activities. *p*-Toluene-thiosulphonic acid is found to be a useful dehydrating catalyst at 280°. Metanilic acid is found to be less active as a dehydrating catalyst.

The three esters of sulphonic acids are less active at 250°, but their activity increases at 280°. Esters of sulphonic acids reduce the hydrolysis of the oil to a certain extent and improve the colour of the dehydrated samples.

Sulphonic acids and their derivatives have shown considerable promise in dehydrating castor oil. A number of sulphonic acids having different substituent groups in the aromatic nucleus have already been studied by Dole and Keskar (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, 38A, 135.). In the present investigation a few sulphonic acids and esters of sulphonic acids have been successfully employed for the dehydration of castor oil.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Dehydration of castor oil was carried out under atmospheric pressure (~713 mm of Hg) and under reduced pressure (20 mm of Hg). The experimental and analytical procedures followed in this investigation are the same as described by Dole and Keskar (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

Values of samples dehydrated at 713 mm pressure.

	Conc. of catalyst.	Dehydration Temp.	Dehydration Time.	I. V.*	H. V.	A. V.	M.W.†	R. I.**	Colour B. R. Y.
1. Anthraquinone-1-sulphonic acid	0.1%	250°	50 min.	145.5	38.3	10.0	1032	1.4762	1 12 12
2. Anthraquinone-2-sulphonic acid	0.1	250°	50	145.8	37.6	10.1	1030	1.4790	1 12 13
3. <i>p</i> -Toluene-thio-sulphonic acid	0.5	280°	50	147.2	19.4	11.3	1092	1.4795	...
4. Metanilic acid	1.0	290°	60	118.7	86.9	7.5	...	...	6 18 10.1
5. Methyl benzene-sulphonate	0.2	280°	50	150.1	7.5	26.2	1151	1.4805	...
6. Ethyl benzene-sulphonate	0.2	280°	50	149.1	18.7	26.7	958.3	1.4805	...
7. Ethyl toluene- <i>p</i> -sulphonate	0.4	280°	40	146.2	23.1	26.9	996.8	1.4780	D. 5.1 10.1

* Iodine value by the Wöbner method at room temperature (27-28°).

† By cryoscopic method using benzene, special for molecular weights.

** Refractive index by Abbe's refractometer at 40°.

Colour: By Lovibond tintometer using 10 mm cell: B - Blue; R - Red; Y - Yellow.

H.V. = hydroxyl value; A.V. = acid value.

TABLE II

Rate of dehydration of castor oil at 713 mm pressure.

No.	Catalyst	Conc. of catalyst.	Temp. of dehydration.	Iodine values of samples drawn at intervals (mins.) of				
				10.	20	30.	40.	50.
1.	Anthraquinone-1-sulphonic acid	0.1%	250°	116.2	128.8	136.1	142.7	145.5
2.	Anthraquinone-2-sulphonic acid	0.1	250°	123.6	132.4	143.3	146.2	146.8
3.	<i>p</i> -Toluene thio-sulphonic acid	0.5	280°	122.6	131.0	138.6	142.5	147.2
4.	Methyl benzene-sulphonate	0.2	280°	116.6	136.2	143.5	145.5	150.1
5.	Ethyl benzene-sulphonate	0.2	280°	125.2	134.7	142.0	144.6	149.1
6.	Ethyl toluene- <i>p</i> -sulphonate	0.4	280°	118.4	134.5	144.5	146.2	144.5

TABLE III

Values of samples dehydrated at 20 mm pressure.

No.	Time of dehydration.	I.V. (Woburn)	II.V.	A.V.	M.W.	R.I. (40°)	Colour.		
							B	R	Y.
1.	50 min.	139.9	27.9	4.9	1018	1.4765	0	2	14
2.	60	141.7	25.6	4.8	1019	...	1	3	17
3.	50	144.4	21.2	6.8	1125	1.4783	0	1	4
4.	50	148.1	10.4	5.3	1055	1.4730	1.9	3	9
5.	50	145.8	24.2	4.5	...	...	1	1.5	5
6.	40	137.2	20.7	4.4	1059	1.4755	0	1.2	10

No. of catalysts, concentration and dehydration temp. are the same as in Table II.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Substitution of Different Groups in Sulphonic Acids.—Dole and Keskar (*loc. cit.*) represented sulphonic acids by the general formula $X-SO_2-OH$, wherein "X" was an alkyl (or substituted alkyl) or aryl (or substituted aryl) radical. The change in the X-part of the molecule was observed to change the properties of the catalyst to a great extent.

In the case of anthraquinone-sulphonic acids (both 1- and 2-), the dehydration is nearly complete with 0.1% of the catalyst at 250° in about one hour. As compared with benzenesulphonic acid, the acid values of the dehydrated samples are less. With the 1-acid, it is 10.0 and with 2-acid, it is 10.1. It seems therefore that the reaction of hydrolysis is suppressed appreciably. The position of the $-SO_2H$ group has practically little influence on the activity of the catalysts. *p*-Toluene-thiosulphonic acid is found to be an active catalyst at 280°. However, the percentage of the acid required to dehydrate the oil is more, viz., 0.5%, when compared with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, viz., 0.3% (*loc. cit.*). It is seen from the rates of dehydration with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid and *p*-toluene-thiosulphonic acid as catalysts that the former is more active than the latter.

Metanilic acid is found inactive as a dehydrating catalyst. This retarding action of the $-\text{NH}_2$ group was also observed by Dole and Keskar (*loc. cit.*).

Esters of Sulphonic Acids.—The esters of sulphonic acids are found to be active, but unlike the free sulphonic acids, they are less active at 250° . When the temperature of dehydration is increased to 280° , the reaction becomes rapid. The reactivity of the esters may be due to their hydrolysis into free sulphonic acids. It may also be assumed that the esters react by way of rupture of the alkyl-oxygen linkage (Ferns and Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 273; Philips, *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 44). When the reactivity of the esters is compared with the corresponding free acids, it is observed that (i) esters are less active than free acids, (ii) in the case of esters, hydrolytic reaction is less, and (iii) comparatively pale coloured dehydrated products are obtained. Moreover, the activities of methyl and ethyl esters are similar.

From the above observations, it is probable that only a part of the ester breaks up into free acid, which is supposed to be responsible for the catalytic reaction.

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DEHYDRATION OF CASTOR OIL BY PHENOL-SUBSTITUTED SULPHONIC ACIDS AND THEIR POTASSIUM SALTS

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Among several phenol-substituted sulphonic acids and their salts, employed as dehydrating catalysts in dehydration of castor oil, *p*-phenol-, *m*-cresol- and resorcinol-sulphonic acids have been found to be active at 250° ; potassium salts of *p*-phenol- and *m*-cresol-sulphonic acids are active both under atmospheric pressure and under reduced pressure; potassium guaiacol-sulphonate is found to be active under atmospheric pressure. Phosphoric acid, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and ammonium dihydrogen phosphate have also been studied as catalysts; among the three, phosphoric acid is found to be a good catalyst, and is reactive at 280° and affords exceptionally pale coloured dehydrated product with low acid value. The other two are found to be inactive.

The use of different naphthol-sulphonic acids as catalysts for dehydration of castor oil was reported by Walton, Coffey and Knapp (*Chem. Abs.*, 1948, 42, 6557). They claimed that 2-naphthol-6-sulphonic acid afforded 100% dehydration of the oil at 260° in one hour with less amount of decomposition of the oil. Dole and Keskar (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, 38A, 135) also found phenol-sulphonic acid to be a useful dehydrating catalyst and observed that the introduction of $-\text{OH}$ group in the benzenesulphonic acid mitigated the tendency of decomposition of the oil without affecting the dehydrating capacity of the catalyst. As a consequence, phenol-sulphonic acid gave paler products than benzenesulphonic acid. Potassium salt of phenol-sulphonic acid was also studied and reported by them to be a good dehydrating catalyst.

In view of the above encouraging results, the use of some more phenol-substituted sulphonic acids as catalysts has been studied in the present investigation.